

LABIO AU LABO 2021 event

D-PhD06-6.10

Responsible Partner: ANSES

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
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Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO-EU <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>

“LABIO AU LABO” 2021 EVENT IN FRENCH PARIS (FRANCE)

<https://labioaulabo.tumblr.com/post/638210749663232001/ciriac-charles-doctorant-de-deuxi%C3%A8me-ann%C3%A9e-en/amp>